

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B0086
 Date: 11 Feb 2005
 Take Off: 10:20:30
 Landing: 15:40:07
 Flight Time: 5h19m37

Trials Instructions: AUTEX – Cirrus Cloud Flight coincident with satellite Overpass
Operating Area: North Sea

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	Mission Scientist 1	Dave Kindred	Met Office
4	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
5	Flight Manager (training)	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Dropsondes / Core Chemistry / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Paul James	FAAM
8	Cloud Physics (training)	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
9	MARSS	Ian Rule	FAAM
10	ARIES	Joss Kent	Met Office
11	SWS	Andy Wilson	Met Office
12	TAFTS	Paul Green	Imperial College
13	TAFTS	Caroline Cox	Imperial College
14	Mission Scientist (training)	Dave Pollard	Met Office
15	Inspector	Paul Shepherd	CAA
16	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B086 Track 11-FEB-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B086
 Date: 11th February, 2005
 Project: Cirrus Studies
 Location: N Sea

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
091322		Start Posn	0.00 kft	129	52'04.36N,0'37.48W
102030		T/O	0.88 kft	245	Cranfield
104631		Videos	11.0 kft	351	UFC & DFC
105017		Transit	11.0 kft	020	
111130	113212	Run 1	0.10 kft	089	100'
111206		Heimann	0.10 kft	088	Cal, SST~6C
112425		Heimann	0.10 kft	083	cal
112927		Heimann	0.10 kft	090	Cal, QNH 1020
113527	113636	Profile 1	50ft - 1.0 kft	307	
113841	114203	Profile 1	1.0 - 4.0 kft	307	Interrupt
114333	114714	Profile 1	4.0 - 8.0 kft	308	Interrupt
114843	120133	Profile 1	8.0 - 20.0 kft	227	Interrupt
120517	121011	Profile 2	20.0 - 15.0 kft	035	1000fpm
121012	122214	Run 2.1	15.0 kft	032	
122441	123641	Run 2.2	15.0 kft	233	
123912	124043	Orbit 1	15.0 kft	329	45deg, right
124149	124315	Orbit 2	15.0 kft	087	45deg, right
124414	124542	Orbit 3	15.0 kft	164	45deg, right
124802	125924	Profile 3	15.1 - 27.0 kft	118	
130226	131109	Profile 3	27.0 - 33.0 kft	299	
131513	132714	Run 3.1	33.0 kft	041	Top of Cirrus
131615		Sonde	33.0 kft	042	Launch 01
131653		Sonde	33.0 kft	041	Launch 02
131827		Contrails	33.0 kft	039	On DFC/RFC
132946	134153	Run 3.2	33.0 kft	217	
134154	134351	Profile 4	33.0 - 31.0 kft	225	1000fpm
134238		Videos	32.3 kft	225	Change tapes
134753	135955	Run 4	31.1 - 31.0 kft	027	
135051		Contrails	31.0 kft	029	On DFC/RFC@1349
135956	140207	Profile 5	31.0 - 29.0 kft	023	
140414	141615	Run 5	29.1 - 29.0 kft	218	
141651	141925	Profile 6	29.1 - 27.0 kft	265	1000fpm
142110	143320	Run 6	27.0 kft	010	
142210		Sonde	27.0 kft	012	Launch 03
143335	143645	Profile 7	27.0 - 24.0 kft	011	
143837	144906	Profile 7	24.1 - 15.0 kft	237	
145309	150809	Run 7	18.0 kft	223	
150920	151750	Profile 8	18.0 - 9.3 kft	221	1000fpm
152033		ASPs	7.5 kft	279	Closed
154007		Land	0.27 kft	331	Cranfield
154515		Stop posn	0.26 kft	306	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W

B086 Track 11-FEB-05

B086 - Sortie for Cirrus Cloud Flight coincident with satellite Overpass 11/02/05

Contacts: Clare Lee, Anthony Baran

Aim:

To measure radiance and in-situ properties of cirrus, by flying below, in and above a particular cloud. This is ideally in coincidence with an AIRS overpass.

Location:

North Sea.

Weather requirements:

Cirrus with clear sky below.

Cirrus tops must be lower than the max aircraft altitude obtainable with fuel load after half the flight time.

NOTAMS:

Flying at 100ft (for SST) and dropping sondes.

Instruments

Radiometers and cloud physics.

(Core consoles, SWS, ARIES, TAFTS, MARSS, Heimann, BBRs, cloud physics, drop sondes.)

Summary:

The aircraft will start by characterising the sea surface and the atmospheric column between the surface and the bottom of the cirrus layer. The ideal case is one where there are no lower clouds below the cirrus. From a level just below the cirrus layer the aircraft will make nadir and zenith measurements with SWS/ARIES and fly banked orbits to characterise the solar and near infrared scattering phase function of the cirrus. A series of straight and level runs within the cirrus characterising the spatial variability of the ice microphysics will be flown at a range of altitudes within the cirrus cloud interleaved with profiles between levels. Finally a series of runs above the cirrus will be flown with ARIES making nadir views. The aim is for the aircraft to be within the cirrus cloud during the actual overpass time.

AQUA 2005/02/11 / AQUA ORBITAL PREDICT PLOT EPOCH DATE: 05/02/10
■ lat: 51.4 lon: 0 AIRS swath angle: 47.3 deg res: 9 km

	Time	Manoeuvre	Duration of flight segment (mins)
1	1015	Transit to North Sea area	50
2	1105	Straight and level run of 10mins duration at 100ft	10
3	1115	Profile ascent from 50ft to altitude 1000ft below cirrus base at 1000ft/min	25
4	1140	Fly two straight and level reciprocal runs oriented across wind each of 12mins below cirrus	30
5	1210	Fly a series of two orbits at closest to solar zenith angle as possible	10
6	1220	Profile ascent to level approx 1000ft above cloud base	5
7	1225	Fly two straight and level reciprocal runs oriented across wind each of 12mins in cirrus. AIRS overpass 12:41 . Drop 1 sonde.	30
8	1255	Profile ascent to level approx 2000ft higher	5
9	1300	Fly straight and level run of 12 mins duration in cirrus.	15
10	1315	Profile ascent to level near cloud tops remaining within cloud	10
11	1325	Fly straight and level run of 12 mins duration in cirrus	15
12	1340	Profile ascent to level 1000ft above cloud tops	10
13	1350	Fly three straight and level reciprocal runs oriented across wind each of 15mins. Drop 1 sonde.	50
14	1440	Transit back to Cranfield	50
15	1530	Land at Cranfield	
		Total Sortie Time	315

Aircraft Scientists Debrief

David Pollard

Flight: B086

11th February 2005

Weather:

A warm front was moving in over the UK from the west during the sortie. At the surface a generally westerly flow existed with the remnants of a wave in the southern North Sea which resulted in a slack gradient with the surface winds light and backing during the day. At altitude a North Westerly jet was well established which led to rapid and untidy development of Ci and As ahead of the warm front.

The aim was to arrive on task in clear air ahead of the development of Ci and then work in and above Ci as the edge progressed South Eastwards.

Sortie:

The aim of this sortie was primarily to use the radiometers in conjunction with in-situ measurements of cloud micro physics to investigate Cirrus.

The early part of the sortie was conducted under nominally clear skies with broken alto-stratus above and consisted of a 20 min run at 100ft to provide simultaneous SST measurements with the Heimann and ARIES. Followed by a series of runs and profiles in order to characterise the cirrus.

The aircraft took off from Cranfield at 10:20 and transited to the operating area in the region of danger area 323 at 6 kft. Upon reaching the coast at Famborough head, it was decided to turn south in search of clearer condition and the first run, **R1**, of 20 mins was conducted at 100 ft below danger area 323 C heading due East. During this run there was a reasonably consistent layer of alto-stratus which cleared somewhat towards the end of the run. Towards the end of the run a slow turn to the north was executed to reposition for the next profile. Throughout the run the wind speed was very low and the sea state calm.

A profile, **P1**, was then started, heading northwards initially until we entered 323B, which by this time had become available to us, from when the profile continued running parallel to the 323 B/C boundary. The profile extended to FL200 encountering some ice crystals at 10.5 kft and a layer of As at 14 kft.

Following this profile it was decided to drop to FL150, **P2**, which was nominally the base of the ice cloud, heading North East, again parallel to the danger area boundary. During the last 3 kft of this profile 2D reported some graupel at low concentrations.

Two reciprocal runs were then conducted, **R2.1 & R2.2**, at FL150 again along the danger area border. These runs were in ice cloud which thinned towards the end of the second leg. 2D concentrations dropped off at the same time but still showed low concentrations of large particle likely to be drop out from a layer of Ci above.

Three orbits were then conducted, **O1, O2 & O3**, with a bank angle of 45°, starboard wing down. The solar zenith angle during these orbits was 68°.

We then profiled up to FL330, **P3**, heading South East to follow the leading edge of the Cirrus, interrupting at FL270 and turning North West to remain in controlled air space.

Two reciprocal runs were then conducted at this level, **R3.1 & R3.2**, initially heading North East and starting in the Ci tops. A pair of Sondes were dropped during R3.1 and they provided good data, except the wind data from Sonde 1. Good contrails were also observed during these runs, and the engine settings photographed. The end of Run 3.2 was in relatively clear conditions. The winds at this level were 42 ms⁻¹/315° consistent with the expected location and orientation of the jet.

We then profiled down to FL310, **P4**, and conducted one run, **R4**, heading North East. Again good contrails were produced and the engine settings photographed. The first half of the run was in clear skies, entering Cirrus during the run which then thickened.

A profile was then conducted to FL290, **P5**, on the same heading and then a reciprocal run, **R5**, undertaken which ended up outside of the Cirrus.

Another profile down to FL270, **P6**, was followed by a run, **R6**, at that level in a relatively clear patch below Cirrus with Sc below.

Following this a profile was undertaken to FL150, **P7**, before deciding to return to the nominal tops of the As at FL180 for a run, **R7**, towards the east. This ended up as a 15 min run which started in cloud with 2D measuring large concentrations of dendrites and possibly wet snow. The cloud then cleared leaving Ci above.

Finally we profiled down to the transit level at FL100, **P8**, and recovered to Cranfield.

David Pollard
16th February 2005

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.086**.....

 Date **11/2/05**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:07					Power c/o
10:12:17					Start Taxi
10:20:32					T/O Cranfield
					St base 12-13kft
					main layer Sc 5/8 @ 3-5kft
10:23					Level @ FL050
					Temp 0.87°C DP -0.22°C
10:25:25					Climbing
10:26					6kft nearly at tops
					one cel at 750
					Clear above
10:31					Clear below
					set Sc As around
10:35					Ci & Cs away to W
10:51					No TWC
10:57					Turning south to find clear air
11:05					Descending to 100ft
					anticipate E→W run towards
					clearer skies
11:11:30	R1	100ft	90		20 min run abt 100ft
					under some Bt As
					clearer ahead
					See smooth wind 3
11:23:05					slow turn to W
11:23:35					ARRIES & Heindorn Ceils

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.026**
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Date 11/2/05

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:25:03					still under in 7/8 A5
					not brilliant
10:29:19					Ries & Fleimann Cals
11:32:12	R1				End of run
					As about wispy ci in pass
11:35:27	A	500ft	307		
11:36:30		1000ft			Interrupt profile
11:39:41		"			Restart
11:42:03		4000ft			Interrupt. to get under 1270
					boundary
11:43:33		4000ft	308		Restart 40 to FL 240
		500ft			As just above
					Think Cs above base in 200ft
11:47:14		FL 80			Interrupt
11:48:43		FL 90	219		Restart
					Running SW 11°C to 3230
					Boundary
11:50:55		FL 100	223		
11:53:					20 running dry
					10.5 hpb
11:54:48					14 hpb passed through A5

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.036**.....

Date11/2/5.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:58:35					Ci thinning down
12:01:33		FL 200	23		End of profile
12:05:47	R2	"			to 2150
					Dropping to FL 150 as
					nominal base of Ci
12:07:16					Entering thick Ci region
		FL 60			Last 2 hft some graupels
12:10:12	R2 R2.1	FL 150	32	54.0 1.2E	end profile of start of run in ice clear
12:22:14	R2.1	FL 150	1	54.1 2.3	End of run turning out recip read
12:24:41	R2.2	FL 150	234	54.6 2.2	Start of run
12:34					20 concentrations down coincident w/ Ci thinning above
12:35					20 low cons of big stuff potentially drop out
12:36	R2.3	FL 150	239	54.1 1.2	20 concentrations up end of run

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B** 66.....
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Date 11/2/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:39:12	01	150	0	54.1/1.0	orbit 1 45° right
12:40:43					started on 330
					End of orbit
					<u>Sat overpass now</u>
12:41:48	02	150	090	m	orbit 2 as above
12:43:15	02				end
					solar zenith angle ←
					86°
12:44:14	03	150 150	180	54.1/1.2	orbit 2 as above
12:45:42	03				end
					next profile to FL300
					for a look down
12:48:02	P3	150	120	53.9/1.4	
12:54		226			RD bar
					top of layer below
					was about ~20 kft
12:59:24		270	117	53.4/3.0	Interrupt at 270 due to SW border
13:02:20		300	300	53.6/3.1	Restart
					going on to 330
13:11:08	P3	330	298	53.7/2.2	end of 330
					turn

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.088**.....

Date 1/2/05

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Ci lower to 100 12
					20 low conc.
					384/88 42 m/s / 315
					etc. Harder
					Clear above
13:15:10	R3.1	330	42	54.0/2.2	start of run in Ci tops
13:16:02				54.1/2.3	Sonde 1
13:16:53					Sonde 2 JPT + CL
13:19:					Controlling sonde 1 oz. xcp wind sonde 2 good + photo of good controlling
					20 still seeing small ice
13:24:32					" concentrations up
13:27:14	R3.1	330	39	54.7/3.8	end
13:27:54					Sonde 1 splash
13:28:44					Sonde 2 splash 20 dropped off
13:29:40	R3.2	330	29	54.5/4.0	Start of run
					20 still see ing
13:41:53	R3.2	330		53.5/3.1	in clear no real Ci below
13:41:54	P4	330			

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B** 086
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Date 11/2/05

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:43:57	P24	310	3	53.4 3	50 - below
13:47:53	R4	310	29		0 - 20
13:50					Controlling well photo 2 o/s temp - 50°C NP - 51.2°C
13:51					20 starting to see low conc.
13:56					20 conc. increasing
13:58					" " " " again
13:59:30	R4	310	23	54.2 3.8	wind was 4.4 m/s / 303 then 9.8 kts / 305
	P5				20 conc. and ptle size inc. at end of run
14:01:50					20 conc. steady size groups end of profile
	P5	290	20	54.4/4.1	
14:04:14	R5	290	220	54.4/3.9	
14:09					20 conc. dropped off
14:12					20 v. low conc.
					Above Ci
					Some cluster stuff ahead & above
14:16:15	R5	290	220	53.5/3	Turning to 270
14:16:57	P6	290	270		down to 270 mid level much below
14:19:25	P6	270		53.4/2.7	

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B**...86.....
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 Date11/2/95.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
14:21:10	R6	270	11	53.3 / 2.6	start of run
14:22:10				53.4 / 2.7	Sonde 3
14:26					20: low conc. aq
14:27:20					20: nothing
14:28					Clear patch S ₂ below
14:32:40					Sonde 3 splash
14:33:20	R6				End
14:33:35	R7				start → 150
14:35					Penetrated a bank
14:36		240			Interrupt R7 firing on recip
14:38					restart R7 D ₂ Ci
14:42					Coming under thicker Ci
14:48					20 seeing small conc. large plates in cloud
14:53:00	R7	180			
14:55:					20: large conc. of droplets + wet snow?
14:57					scanning cloud tops
15:02					R7: low, stable conc.
					In clear slot Ci above checking As below
15:08:09	R7	180			End in clear slot Ci above
15:09:17	R8	180	221	52.8 / 1.4	Start
15:10					Into cloud
15:15					in clear slot
15:17:8	R8				end end 5-min

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B086

Date: 11/2/05

Operator: papj

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP Block Transfer	SID1 Particle Count	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Me an R			Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
111130	PCASP NOT WORKING V=4.6										Start run 1 @ 100ft
113212											End run 1
113527											Start p1 @ 80ft
113636											010
114005											020
114104											030
114203											040
114440											050
114540											060
114620											070
114713											080
115054											100
115134					10	800	3	1000	2000	3	110
115257					20	800	3	2000	2000	3	120
115350					10	800	3	2000	2000	3	130
115450					20	800	3	1000	1000	3	140
115558					20	800	3	2200	1000	3	150
115700					20	800	3	2200	1500	3	160
1158					10	800	3/9	1000	1000	3/9	170
115927					10	600	10	700			180
1201					10	400	10				190
120133					20	200	10				200
120517					10	400	10	3000	400	10	Start p2@200
120610					10	400	10	1000	400	10	190
120710					20	600	3/9	500	1000	3/9	180
120806					20	800	3/9	4000	1500	3/9	170
120908					20	800	3/9	2500	2000	3/9	160
121012					20	800	3/9	3000	1500	3/9	150 end p2 & start run 2.1
1211					10	800	3/9	3000	1500	3/9	
1213					10	800	3/9	2000	1000	3/9	
1214					20	800	3/9	2000	1000	3/9	
1215					20	800	3/9	3500	1000	3/9	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

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Operator: papj

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
1216					10	800	3/9	2500	1000	3/9	
1217					20	800	8	3500	1000	8	
1218					20	800	8	4000	1000	8	
1219					20	800	8	4000	1000	8	
1220					40	800	8	4000	1000	8	
1221					30	800	8	6000	800	8	
1222					20	800	8	4000	800	8	
122214											End run 2.1
122441											Start run 2.2
1225					40	800	8	6500	1000	8	
1226					40	800	8	7000	1000	8	
1227					20	500	8	4000	1000	8	
1228					20	800	8	4000	1500	8	
1229					20	600	8	2500	1000	8	
1230					20	600	8	3000	1000	8	
1231					20	800	8	4000	1000	8	
1232					20	800	8	3000	1000	8	
1233					10	800	8	500	1000	8	
1234					5	800	8	500	1500	8	
1235					20	800	8	400	1500	8	
1236					40	500	8	5000	1000	8	
123641											End of run 2.2
124802											Start p3@150
124850					10	800	8		1000	8	
124950					10	800	8		1000	8	
125050					50	600	8		800	8	
125150					5	400	8				
125245					5	200	10				
125340											
125435											
125526											
125626											
125720											

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B086

Date:11/2/05

Operator:papj

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
125820											260
											270
13345											280
1305											290
											320
131109											330 end p3
131513											Start run 3.1 @330
1317					20	100					
1318					20	100					
1319					20	100					
1320					10	100					
1321					10	100					
1322					20	100					
1323					30	100					
1324					40	100					
1325					30	150					
1326					30	125					
1327					40	125					
132714											End of run3.1
132946											Start run 3.2 @330
1330					50	125					
1331					12	100					
1332					10	100					
1333					10	75					
1334					30	125					
1335					43	100					
1336					10	125					
1338					4	125					
1339					5	75					
134154											End run 32
1345					40	500					FI 31
134351											P4 end

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B086

Date: 11/2/05

Operator: j trembath (training) Page 4 of 6

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
134753											
1352					7						
1353					14						
1354					6						
1355					7						
1356					9						
1357					22						
1358					92						
1359					125						
135955											
1401					106						
1402					48						
140207											
140414											
1405					100						
1406					200						
1407					99						
1408					90						
1409					50						
1410					40						
1411					40						
1412											
141615											
141651											
141806											
141925											
142110											
1424					10	250					
1425											
1426					30	250	8				
1427					5	200	8				

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B086

Date: 11/2/05

Operator: j trembath

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
1428					6	200	8				
1429					25	225	8				
1430					3	400	8				
1431					5	250	8				
1432					20	250	8				
1433					20	250	8				
143320											End run 6.1 fl 270
143335											P7 fl270
1434					10	250	8				260
1435					90	300	8				250
											240
143645											Fl240 interrupt p7
143837											Recom p4 240
											230
1441											220
1442					4	350	8				210
1443					5	570	8	3000	1000	8	200
1445					2	450	8	2000	800	8	190
1446								2000	800	8	180
1447								300	800	8	170
1448					3	450	9	800	800	8	160
144906											End p7
145309											Start run 7.1 @ 180
1454					30	550	9	2000	2000	8	
1455					10	700	9	2000	1000	8	
1456					5	800		2000	1000	8	
1456					5	500	8	250	1000	8	
1457					Missed recording						
1458					5	450	8	3000	800	8	
1459					5	625	8	2500	800	8	
1500					5	359	8	2500	600	8	
1501					5	400	8	4500	600	8	

SWS Viewing Directions

	Time	Manoeuvre	Duration of flight segment (mins)
1	1015	Transit to North Sea area <i>In level parts: NADIR</i>	50
2	1105	Straight and level run of 10mins duration at 100ft ZENITH	10 20 ✓
3	1115	Profile ascent from 50ft to altitude 1000ft below cirrus base at 1000ft/min	25 ✓
4	1140	Fly two straight and level reciprocal runs oriented across wind each of 12mins below cirrus ZENITH Very last 2 minutes: NADIR	30 ✓
5	1210	Fly a series of two ³ orbits at closest to solar zenith angle as possible ZENITH	10 ✓
6	1220	Profile ascent to level approx 1000ft above cloud base	5 ✓
7	1225	Fly two straight and level reciprocal runs oriented across wind each of 12mins in cirrus. AIRS overpass 12:41. Drop 1 sonde. ZENITH	30
8	1255	Profile ascent to level approx 2000ft higher	5
9	1300	Fly straight and level run of 12 mins duration in cirrus. ZENITH	15 ✓
10	1315	Profile ascent ^{descend} to level near cloud tops remaining within cloud <i>FL 2910</i>	10 ✓
11	1325	Fly straight and level run of 12 mins duration in cirrus ZENITH	15 ✓
12	1340	Profile ascent to level 1000ft above cloud tops	10 ✓
13	1350	Fly three ^{two} straight and level reciprocal runs oriented across wind each of 15mins. Drop 1 sonde. NADIR Very last 2 minutes: ZENITH	50
14	1440	Transit back to Cranfield <i>In level parts: NADIR</i>	50
15	1530	Land at Cranfield	
		Total Sortie Time	315

~~Filters~~
~~Filtered~~
11/2/04 This
Second run.
No filters

SWS/SHIMS PRE-FLIGHT LOG		Date	11/2/05	Flight	B086
Operator(s)	A. Wilson		Campaign		
Departure	11	Arrival	11		

Physical system setup

Module Number	Connection(e.g.SWS nir, SHIMS upper)
0	SWS
27581	SWS

System functionality check After system stabilizes

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0 Sec	at time	100000Z
Freezer temp	-5°C			

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 086	Date	11/2/05	Operator(s)	A. Wilson	log page	2	of	3
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks			
				Vis	NIR				

122011			180	150	750	dark			
122040	R2.1	150	180	150	750	data	NADIR	NADIR	
122214	R2.1					end	R2.1		
1222 19 19		150	0°	50	300	dark	Zenith	Zenith	774
122355		150	0°	60	300	data	Zenith	view	
122441	R2.2	150	0°	50	300	start	R2.2		
123340	R2.2	150	180°	150	750	dark			
123402		150	180°	150	750	data	NADIR	view	
123641	R2.2	150	180	150	750	end	R2.2		
123705						data	stop		
123804			6°F	50	300	dark			
123912	orbit 1		6°F	50	300	orbit	45°	Right wing down	
124016			6°F	15	150	plark	0.4	secs sample.	
124035						data			
124043	orbit 1	150	6°F	15	150				
124149	orbit 2	150	6°F	15	150	start	orbit 2	0.2 secs sample	
124315	---	150	6°F	15	150	end	orbit 2		
124318	orbit 3	150	6°F	15	100	dark			
124322	---	150	6°F	15	100	data			
124414	orbit 3	150	6°F	15	100	start	orbit 3	0.2 secs sample	
124542	--- 3	150	6°F	15	100	end	orbit 3		
1247 52		150	0°	50	300	dark			
124802	P3	150	0°	50	300	start	P3		
124805		150	0°	50	300	data	- Zenith	view	
125924	P3	270	0°	50		interrupt	P3		
130226	P3	270	0°	50	300	restart	P3		
130650		300	0°	300	750	dark		1 sec sample.	
130727		306	0°	300	750	data			
131109	P3	330	0°	300	750	end	P3 @ FL330		
131513	R3.1	330	0°	300	750	start	of R3.1		
131516						Sonde	1		
131653						Sonde	2		
132714	R3.1	330	0°	300	750	end	R 3.1		
132946	R3.2	330	0°	300	750	start	R3.2		
134154	R3.2	330	0°	300	750	end	R3.2		
134154	P4	330 →	0°	300	750	start	P4 → FL310		
134351	P4	310	0°	300	750	end	P4 @ FL310		
134753	R4	310	0°	300	750	start	R4		
135940				200	750	dark			
135955						data			
135955	R4	310	0°	200	750	end	R4		
	P5	310 →	0°	200	750	start	P5		

MS Pitch 5.95

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 086	Date	11/2/05	Operator(s)	A. Wilson	log page	1	of	3
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	MIRR Pos	Int Times		Remarks			
				Vis	NIR				

101640			90°A				Video start during taxi		
102035	Transit		90°A				take off.		
102400	"		90°A	30	30		Dark current		
102454	"		90°A	30	30		data record		
102535	"		180	30	30		looking down		
103140	"		180	400	400		dark		
103220	"	100	180	400	400		data		
103400		110	180	400	400		PC Reboot - network problem		
104630		110	180	400	400		Dark - network restored		
104650		110	180	400	400		Data		
105240		110	180	"	"		Flying over green fields		
105255		"	"	"	"		" " " " water		
105900		075	180	"	"		descending		
110132		055	0°	250	500		dark		
110153		"	"	"	"		data		
110307			0°	100	750		dark		
110332		040	0°	100	750		data		
111040				30	350		dark		
111059	R1	100ft	0°	30	350		dark R1 started 111130.		
111235	R1	100ft	0°	75	500		dark		
111350	R1	100ft	0°	75	500		data		
112130	R1	100ft	0°	50	350		dark		
112156	R1	100ft	0°	50	350		data		
113212	R1	100ft	0°	50	350		end of R1		
113527	P1	50ft	0°	50	350		start P1 → 100ft below ci base.		
113636	P1	100ft	0°	50	350		int P1 @ 100ft		
113841	P1	100ft	0°	50	350		restart P1		
114108		350ft	0°	150	500		dark		
114124			0°	150	500		data		
114203	P1	400ft	0°	150	500		int P1 @ 400ft		
114333	P1						restart P1		
114341			0°	100	500		dark		
114359	P1		0°	100	500		data		
115040							Video stop		
115105							Video restart		
115648	P1	165	0°	50	300		dark		
115715	P1	165	0°	50	300		data		
120133	P1	200	0	50	300		int P1 @ FL200		
120517	P2	200 →	0°	50	300		start P2 → FL150		
121012	P2	150	0°	50	300		end P2		
	P2.1	150	0°	50	300		P2.1		
12108		150	180°	50	300		change to NADIR view.		

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	11/02/05	Flight	B086	log pages
Operator(s)	Ian Rule		Campaign	Cirrus studies		
Departure	Cranfield		Arrival	Cranfield		

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection	tick					
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers	tick					
Close all MARSS circuit breakers	tick					
FERA on						at time 0810 ish
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	°C	Ch	°C	Ch18	°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on						at time 0810 ish
Initial target temperatures	Hot	ambient	Cold	The same		
Target heating						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Scanning on (LMD box)						at time 0810 ish
Scan indication	Monitor	tick	Visual	tick		

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software						at time
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication	Monitor	tick	Visual	tick		
Weather	Cloud	8/8 SCu		Precip	Light dz	
	Surface	damp		Pressure	1008	
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} + 0$		at time 0915			
Brightness temps 'sensible'						
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344		Cold	285
	Deimos:	Hot	Cold			
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16 (40-44)	Ch17 (45-49)	Ch18 (40-44)	Ch19 (40-44)	Ch20 (44-48)	
	1	36	39	39	43	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again						at time

ARIES flight log

Flight: B086

Location: North Sea

page

of

Date: 11/2/05

Operator(s): Joss Renn

Resolution: 128

Gain A: 2

B: 4

Notes: 090845 Started logging data

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
092926	One	B086B	CSD	51.2	22.6	14.8	-1899			
102748	Transit Ascent	B086C	CSD	51.5	22.5	12.6	-1899	24.2	CHCAL X5	
103850	Transit	B086D	AW	51.1	22.6	9.2	-189.3	23.4	NIMINA X2	FL110
104640	FL110	B086E	CSD	51.5	22.3	7.1	-189.3	22.2	CHCAL X1	
104910	FL110	B086F	CSD	51.2	22.5	7.1	-1899	21.0	NIMINA X2	
109231	FL110	B086G	CSD	51.2	22.4	6.3	u	19.7	CHCAL	end
109523	FL110	B086H	CSD	50.9	21.9	6.0	u	20.3	NIMINA X	
109944	FL110	B086I	CSD	51.2	22.0	4.9	u	18.6	CHCAL	
110309	FL110	B086J	AW	51.2	22.3	5.1	u	19.5	CHCAL	
110553	FL100'	B086K	CSD	51.2	22.6	7.1	u	19.8	CHCAL	20 min run / scans ok
111502	100'	B086L	CSD	51.1	22.5	8.1	u	19.7	NIMINA	X2 · scans ok
111812	100'	B086M	CSD	51.1	22.4	9.2	u	18.8	CHCAL	scans ok
112027	106'	B086N	CSD	51.0	22.3	9.7	u	19.2	NIMINA	X2
112339	106'	B086O	CSD	51.3	22.2	10.3	b	16.4	CHCAL	
112549	100'	B086P	CSD	51.1	22.4	10.8	u	10.5	NIMINA	X2
112921	106'	B086Q	CSD	51.2	22.4	11.1	u	11.1	CHCAL	
115177	FL100'	B086R	CSD	51.2	22.4	8.4	-189.9	8.3	CHCAL	
121012	FL150	B086S	AW	51.0	22.1	0.6	-189.3	18.6	CHCAL	R2-1
121236	FL150	B086T	AW	50.5	22.1	-0.2	u	17.8	NIMINA.	X2 R2-1

ARIES flight log

Fflight: 13086

Location: North Sea

page 2 of

Date: 11/2/05

Operator(s): Joss Reni

Resolution: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 4

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shttr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
121548	R2.1 FL40	13086 U	Clsd	51-2	22-7	-1.7	-189.9		CHCAL	
121758	R2.1 FL50	13086 V	Open	51-1	22-3	-1.9	-189.3	15.7	ZIMINA.	x2
122105	R2.1 FL50	13086 W	Clsd	51-2	22.5	-2.9	" "	14.2	CHCAL	
122441	R2.2 FL50	13086 X	Clsd	50-8	22.2	-2.11	" "	18.9	CHCAL CHCAL	Stall on thin ice cloud
122654	R2.2 FL50	13086.Y	Clsd	51-0	21.8	-2.2	" "	19.8	NIMINA	x2 " "
123001	R2.2 FL50	13086 Z	Clsd	51-1	22.1	-2.2	" "	18.0	CHCAL	
123248	R2.2 FL50	13086 a	Clsd	50-9	22.5	-2.2	" "	18.6	NIMINA.	x2
123532	R2.2 FL50	13086 b	Clsd	51-2	22.2	-1.9	" "	16.8	CHCAL	
123855	R2.2 FL50	13086 c	Clsd	50-9	22.1	-1.9	" "	17.7	CHCAL	Orbit 1 FL50 450
124130	Orbit 2	13086 d	Open	50-9	22.2	-1.8	" "	15.9	ZIMINA	x2 orbit 2 burstward
124415	Orbit 3	13086 e	Clsd	51-2	22-3	-2.3	" "	13.7	CHCAL	orbit 3 early
124410	Reset software - to reset file counter.									
1257	restored data recording									
125901	R3 FL270	13086 S	Clsd	51-4	22-4	-3.7	-189.9	16.4	CHCAL	
131517	R3.1 FL330	13086 b	Clsd	51-0	22.6	-13.2	-189.9	16.4	CHCAL	
131735	R3.1 FL330	13086 c	Clsd	50-9	22.0	-14.6	-189.9	15.9	NIMINA	x2
132046	R3.1 FL330	13086 d	Clsd	51-0	22.2	-17.7	" "	13.7	CHCAL	
132200	R3.1 FL330	13086 e	Clsd	50-9	22.2	-14.0	" "	15.3	NIMINA	x2
132612	R3.4 FL330	13086 f	Clsd	51-0	22.3	-20.9	" "	14.3	CHCAL	

ARIES flight log

Flight: *B086*

Location: *North Sea*

page *3* of *3*

Date: *11/2/05*

Operator(s): *Joss Kent*

Resolution: *1*

Gain A: *2* B: *4*

Notes: *Cirrus flight.*

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
<i>132956</i>	<i>R3-2FL330</i>	<i>C086B</i>	<i>Clsd</i>	<i>508</i>	<i>223</i>	<i>-21.5</i>	<i>-189.9</i>	<i>17.6</i>	<i>CHCAL</i>	
<i>133200?</i>	<i>R3.2 FL330</i>	<i>C086C</i>	<i>Clsd</i>	<i>509</i>	<i>220</i>	<i>-220</i>	<i>~</i>	<i>17.2</i>	<i>NIMINA X 2</i>	
<i>133341</i>	<i>R3.2 FL330</i>	<i>C086D</i>	<i>Clsd</i>	<i>509</i>	<i>221</i>	<i>-23.1</i>	<i>-189.3</i>	<i>16.1</i>	<i>NIMINA x 1</i>	
<i>133520</i>	<i>R3.2 FL330</i>	<i>C086E</i>	<i>Clsd</i>	<i>509</i>	<i>223</i>	<i>-24.1</i>	<i>-189.9</i>	<i>14.7</i>	<i>CHCAL</i>	
<i>133746</i>	<i>R3.2 FL330</i>	<i>C086F</i>	<i>Clsd</i>	<i>509</i>	<i>221</i>	<i>-24.3</i>	<i>-189.3</i>	<i>15.7</i>	<i>NIMINA x 2</i>	
<i>134048</i>	<i>R3.2 FL330</i>	<i>C086G</i>	<i>Clsd</i>	<i>510</i>	<i>220</i>	<i>-24.3</i>	<i>~</i>	<i>14.4</i>	<i>CHCAL</i>	
<i>134753</i>	<i>R4 FL310</i>	<i>C086H</i>	<i>Clsd</i>	<i>508</i>	<i>223</i>	<i>-25.0</i>	<i>-189.3</i>	<i>18.2</i>	<i>CHCAL</i>	
<i>135010</i>	<i>R4 FL310</i>	<i>C086I</i>	<i>Clsd</i>	<i>510</i>	<i>215</i>	<i>-25.0</i>	<i>~</i>	<i>17.6</i>	<i>NIMINA x 2</i>	
<i>135318</i>	<i>R4 FL310</i>	<i>C086J</i>	<i>Clsd</i>	<i>509</i>	<i>223</i>	<i>-25.5</i>	<i>~</i>	<i>14.0</i>	<i>CHCAL</i>	
<i>135527</i>	<i>R4 FL310</i>	<i>C086K</i>	<i>Clsd</i>	<i>507</i>	<i>224</i>	<i>-25.3</i>	<i>-189.3</i>	<i>15.2</i>	<i>NIMINA x 2</i>	
<i>135826</i>	<i>R4 FL310</i>	<i>C086L</i>	<i>Clsd</i>	<i>510</i>	<i>214</i>	<i>-25.7</i>	<i>-189.3</i>	<i>14.0</i>	<i>CHCAL</i>	
<i>140417</i>	<i>R5 FL290</i>	<i>C086M</i>	<i>Clsd</i>	<i>509</i>	<i>222</i>	<i>-25.1</i>	<i>~</i>	<i>18.0</i>	<i>CHCAL</i>	
<i>140627</i>	<i>R5 FL290</i>	<i>C086N</i>	<i>Clsd</i>						<i>NIMINA x 1</i>	
<i>140807</i>	<i>R5 FL290</i>	<i>C086O</i>	<i>Clsd</i>	<i>509</i>	<i>223</i>	<i>-25.0</i>	<i>-189.3</i>	<i>14.6</i>	<i>NIMINA x 1</i>	
<i>140949</i>	<i>R5 FL290</i>	<i>C086P</i>	<i>Clsd</i>	<i>510</i>	<i>223</i>	<i>-24.9</i>	<i>-189.3</i>	<i>14.2</i>	<i>CHCAL</i>	
<i>141209</i>	<i>R5 FL290</i>	<i>C086Q</i>	<i>Clsd</i>	<i>510</i>	<i>223</i>	<i>-24.9</i>	<i>~</i>	<i>15.4</i>	<i>NIMINA x 2</i>	
<i>141509</i>	<i>R5 FL290</i>	<i>C086R</i>	<i>Clsd</i>	<i>510</i>	<i>220</i>	<i>-24.3</i>	<i>~</i>	<i>14.2</i>	<i>CHCAL</i>	
<i>142112</i>	<i>R6 FL270</i>	<i>C086S</i>	<i>Clsd</i>	<i>510</i>	<i>222</i>	<i>-23.3</i>	<i>~</i>	<i>18.2</i>	<i>CHCAL</i>	
<i>142323</i>	<i>R6 FL270</i>	<i>C086T</i>	<i>Clsd</i>	<i>510</i>	<i>225</i>	<i>-22.9</i>	<i>~</i>	<i>18.0</i>	<i>NIMINA x 2</i>	

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

FLIGHT: B086	DATE: 11/02/2005	OPERATOR: Doug Anderson	PAGE: 1 of 1
LOCATION: N Sea		PROJECT: AUTEX	

GAS CYLINDER PRESSURES	Argon/CO2	N2	CO	HORACE
PRE FLIGHT	160 bar	20 bar	143 bar	-- n/a --
POST FLIGHT	155 bar	0 bar	143 bar	-- n/a --
Instrument time check	-	-	11:18:41	11:18:41

TIME (GMT)	HEIGHT (Flight Level)	RUN #	CO SENSITIVITY (Hz/ppbV)	CO BACKGROUND (ppb)	CO BCKGRD.CNT.B (Hz)	CO CONC. (ppb V)	O3 (ppb)	NO (ppb)	NO2 (ppb)	NOx (ppb)	SO2 (ppb)			
10/02/05	-	-	90.51	80.69	7303.25	-	-	-	-	-	-			
14:55:06	Remarks: Last calibration from previous flight/ground test for comparison with today.													
11/02/05	FL110	Transit	93.00	77.78	7233.85	117.362	43	0.08	0.25	0.33	-			
10:45:39	Flow Lamp:	34.00	Press Monocr	1.17	Press Cell:	6.79	Press Cal Gas	2.06	Lamp °C	49.63	Monocr °C	23.61	PMT °C	23.57
Remarks: ASP opened. CO cal max values : 543 - 527														
11:04:47	FL050	-	91.71	76.70	7033.60	127.401	38	-0.14	0.46	0.32	-			
	Flow Lamp:	34.01	Press Monocr	1.21	Press Cell:	7.15	Press Cal Gas	2.08	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	24.04	PMT °C	23.99
Remarks: CO cal max values : 506 - 512 Descent started @ 11:03:03, part way through cal														
11:14:22	100'	R1	91.57	77.15	7064.89	139.775	26	1.44	3.97	5.62	-			
	Flow Lamp:	34.06	Press Monocr	1.23	Press Cell:	7.15	Press Cal Gas	2.10	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	24.04	PMT °C	23.99
Remarks: CO cal max values : 514 - 521 Cal combined with Heimann/ARIES - 53 55' N running Eastwards														
11:44:20	Remarks: FL040: O ₃ A & B flows both just above 0.5 rather than around 1.0 as normal. At FL080 both read 0.75													
12:13:07	FL150	R2.1	90.64	79.48	7203.72	110.966	39	-0.03	0.20	0.19	-			
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C	
Remarks: CO cal max values : 511 - 517 Cal started with start of run call @ 11:12:12														
13:14:10	FL330	-	82.89	118.80	9847.80	-	54	0.19	0.14	0.34	-			
	Flow Lamp:	33.84	Press Monocr	0.99	Press Cell:	4.96	Press Cal Gas	1.86	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	24.42	PMT °C	24.34
Remarks: CO cal max values : 507 - 499 Vent capped @ FL250														
13:46:48	FL310	Pre R4	84.30	110.04	9275.67	99.044	54	0.02	0.11	0.13	-			
	Flow Lamp:	33.62	Press Monocr	0.99	Press Cell:	5.07	Press Cal Gas	1.85	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	24.35	PMT °C	24.24
Remarks: CO cal max values : 513 - 521														
14:22:31	FL270	-	87.52	96.18	8417.82	102.896	53	0.03	0.37	0.40	-			
	Flow Lamp:	33.83	Press Monocr	1.04	Press Cell:	5.40	Press Cal Gas	1.91	Lamp °C	50.0	Monocr °C	24.78	PMT °C	24.21
Remarks: CO cal max values : 522 - 530														
14:55:	FL180		91.08	81.23	7398.02	106.939	44	-0.11	0.27	0.17	-			
	Flow Lamp:	33.91	Press Monocr	1.12	Press Cell:	6.16	Press Cal Gas	22.00	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	24.24	PMT °C	24.18
Remarks: CO cal max values : 524 - 531 Vent cap removed @ FL180 " 14:55:05														
::	FL										-			
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C	
Remarks: CO cal max values :														
::	FL										-			
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C	
Remarks: CO cal max values :														
::	FL										-			
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C	
Remarks: CO cal max values :														
::	Remarks:													
::	Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values :													

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B086**

Date: 11/02/05

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Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	<u>Probes</u>		
GPS		Y	FFSSP	Y	Y
Satcom C		Y	PCASP	Y	Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-P	Y	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C	Y	Y
De-Iced Temp		Y	Cloudscope	Y	N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 1	Y	Y
Heimann		Y	SID 2	N	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP100	N	
G. Eastern		Y	CIP 2	N	
J. Williams		Y	CPI	N	
Nevzorov		Y	HVPS		
TWC	Y	N	<u>Racks:</u>		
FWVS	N		INC	N	
<u>Radiometers</u>			CCN / CNC	Y	N
Upper Clear	N		CVI	Y	N
" Red	N				
" Silicon	N		<u>Aerosol</u>		
" JO1D	N		PSAP	Y	N
Lower Clear		Y	Nephelometer	Y	N
" Red		Y	Filters	Y	N
" Silicon		Y	AMS	Y	N
" JO1D	N		VACC	Y	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			LTI	Y	N
TAFTS	Y	Y			
MARSS	Y	Y			
DEIMOS	Y	Y			
ARIES	Y	Y			
SWS	Y	Y			
<u>Chemistry</u>					
Ozone		Y			
ECGC	N				
NOX		Y			
CO		Y	<u>Others:</u>		
ORAC	Y	N			
PAN	Y	N			
PERCA	Y	N			
WAS	Y	N			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B086

Date: 11/02/05

Instruments

1. LBBRS – Aft BBR (Clear H490) found to have inner and outer domes full of water on the preflight. Removed before flight.
2. Cameras – DFC and RFC no pictures preflight. Found they were being swapped over by Avalon. When external panel closed up, DFC still not working. Avalon checked then okay. In flight, RFC picture black for most of the flight.
3. TWC – Para 77 ISRC out of range on preflight, 2300 DRSU. It would switch to within range for about 5 seconds, the detector would come up for a few seconds then the source current would switch back to the out of range level and the detector goes off. Switched probe off after t/o.
4. INU – Momentary “inertial sensor fail” message on INU status page. Then later 1432 “In Manual Magnetic Heading”.
5. Inboard VCR – as on previous flight, keeps going into standby mode so no picture displayed on screen but otherwise operating normally.
6. Outboard VCR – front cover came off after landing. Stowed in CorCon drawer.

Dropsondes – 3 launched, problem with winds data on one

ARIES – Good

MARSS – Good except CH16

SWS – Good

Cloud Physics – Okay except for PCASP

Core Chemistry – Good

TAFTS – Good

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom H – 1 call by DFL

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B086:

Log	Reason
TAFTS	No log is taken for TAFTS

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	21 Mar 2005	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing ASXX
r1	3 Oct 2006	Doug Anderson	ASXX and Missing logs/video log page added
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2? x Upward Facing Cameras

2? x Down/Rearward Facing Cameras

8mm video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dr Jonathan P. Taylor

Manager Atmospheric Radiation Research Group
Met Office
Cordouan 2 W079
FitzRoy Road
Devon
EX1 3PB
UK

Tel: +44 (0)1392 884647

Fax: +44 (0)1392 885681

E-mail: jonathan.p.taylor@metoffice.gov.uk